

Green Europe? Lobbying in the European Union using the example of climate policy

Developed by: planpolitik

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Keywords

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Introduction

Green Europe? Lobbying in the EU: Using the Example of Climate Policy is a blended-learning simulation game that places participants in the midst of environmental policymaking within the European Union (EU). Developed and delivered via planpolitik's digital simulation platform, Senaryon, the game explores how different stakeholders - ranging from European Commission (EC) services to industry, consumer, and environmental lobby groups - collaborate and compete to influence legislative proposals to reduce CO2 emissions from cars.

Repeatedly, participants from multiple universities, including the Georg-August-Universität Göttingen and the University of Antwerp, have used this simulation to engage across countries, time zones, and academic programs, gaining firsthand experience of the EU's complex interplay between policy drafting and lobbying activities. This cross-university setup enables collaboration between diverse educational backgrounds and mirrors the distributed nature of EU policy work. The game may be used entirely online and asynchronously, in a blended format that combines online preparation with face-to-face elements, or entirely on-site with digital support. Below, we focus on the blended/online iteration. Its mixed-format design builds on established approaches to combining online and in-person simulation elements (Raiser et al., 2018).

Facts

Release date:	2019
Developer:	planpolitik
Game type:	Blended, online, and on-site variants
Number of players:	Multiplayer (recommended 20–50 participants)
Format:	Hybrid
Time frame:	Typically 2 weeks online (split into two 1-week phases), with an optional 1–2 days of on-site negotiations
Languages:	English, other translations possible

Environment:	Access to a laptop, tablet, or smartphone for digital play
Material:	Provided through the Senaryon platform (role descriptions, chat systems, shared text pads)
Price:	Implementation can be facilitated by planpolitik trainers or self-facilitated by teaching staff. Costs apply in both scenarios

Resonance & Criticism

Reflections from repeated iterations show that the simulation is perceived as realistic, motivating, and helpful in understanding lobbying, negotiation, and amendment processes in EU climate policy. Students value practical insights, dual-role play, and cross-national collaboration. Challenges include compressed timelines, uneven engagement, and simplified conflict dynamics. Digital coordination across time zones can be demanding, though the platform is generally viewed as accessible.

Game principle & Process

Figure 1. Example interface from *Green Europe? Lobbying in the European Union*, showing role-specific workspaces, publications, and task coordination within the online simulation environment (planpolitik). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

First week: Policy drafting in the European Commission. During the first phase, half of the participants play the role of EU Commission officials in DG Environment, DG Industry, and DG Trade (see Figure 1). Their task is to draft concrete legislative proposals to reduce CO2 emissions from cars. They begin with broad goals (e.g., setting emission targets) and gradually move toward specific policy measures (e.g., taxation incentives, emission standards). Meanwhile, the other half of the participants act as lobbyists representing diverse interests - environmental NGOs, trade associations, airlines, consumer protection organizations, and more.

Working asynchronously, each team completes clearly defined sub-tasks with deadlines. The commission teams consult one another to reconcile conflicting interests among different DGs, while the lobbyist teams collaborate to develop position papers and strategic outreach. All interactions—negotiations, information exchange, and brainstorming—occur via Senaryon’s built-in chat system and shared text documents. Facilitators monitor these interactions, provide concise feedback, and guide the next steps.

Second week: Decision-making in the European Parliament. The second phase simulates the legislative procedure in the European Parliament (EP). Participants switch roles: those previously serving in the Commission now become lobbyists, and those who were lobbyists become Members of the European Parliament (MEPs). The MEPs organize themselves into political groups (e.g., the European People’s Party, the Greens, the Socialists, etc.) and propose amendments to the Commission’s legislative draft.

Again, participants communicate asynchronously online. MEPs must translate overarching ideological standpoints into specific amendments, while lobbyists engage them with arguments, data, and strategic persuasion. By the end of the second phase, the EP votes on a resolution that consolidates the amendments made to the Commission’s proposal.

After both phases, each participant composes a reflection essay or report detailing how the negotiations unfolded, how positions shifted, and what they learned about EU lobbying and decision-making processes.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

This simulation game deepens participants’ understanding of the EU legislative process, specifically how the European Commission and the European Parliament interact under the watchful (and influential) eye of lobby groups. Learners actively experience the complexity of reaching consensus among conflicting interests, honing both their analytical and practical skills in policy drafting and advocacy. Role-switching exposes participants to differing strategic logics and pressures within EU policymaking, illustrating how institutional mandates and lobbying goals diverge.

In addition to political science and European studies programs, “Green Europe?” can be integrated into interdisciplinary courses dealing with environmental policy, international

relations, or public administration. The experience aligns with active learning strategies: it challenges participants to collaborate on real-world tasks—drafting legislation, negotiating positions, building coalitions. The game also supports intercultural competence, as students from different countries and academic backgrounds work in distributed teams. This reflects broader findings that online simulation formats can expand international and digital teaching capacities in higher education (Ivens & Kaiser, 2021). Non-academic settings, such as NGOs or think tanks, can adopt this format for professional training on climate negotiations or EU lobbying tactics.

Effectiveness

Instructors from Georg-August-Universität Göttingen and the University of Antwerp report high levels of student engagement and satisfaction. By mixing groups from multiple institutions, the simulation makes full use of asynchronous online collaboration tools and fosters a genuine international atmosphere. Students consistently highlight the value of working in cross-national teams, learning to divide tasks efficiently—one member may focus on research, another on drafting position papers, and a third on stakeholder outreach. This aligns with insights from collaborative online simulation research, which highlights how distributed teams benefit from structured digital environments (Fink, Bursens & Harzem 2023).

Early evaluations suggest that the two-phased structure enhances the depth and pace of learning. The deadlines embedded in each phase create a sense of urgency, preventing the common pitfall of asynchronous simulations, which can sometimes stall. Instead, structured tasks lead to lively online debates, immediate supervisor feedback, and tangible learning outcomes. Reflective essays show that participants gain a clearer understanding of lobbying strategies, legislative constraints, and the role of both environmental and industrial perspectives in shaping EU climate policy.

Note that although feedback has been gathered from several implementations of the simulation game, no empirical, peer-reviewed studies evaluating the game's effectiveness have yet been conducted.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

By foregrounding lobbying strategies and interest-based negotiation, the simulation may place less emphasis on normative, procedural, and ethical constraints that also structure EU climate policymaking. Without careful facilitation and debriefing, participants may develop an oversimplified understanding of lobbying influence, overestimating strategic pressure while underestimating institutional safeguards, transparency requirements, and evidence-based deliberation. In addition, the asynchronous format can lead to unequal participation levels, with more active participants exerting disproportionate influence on outcomes, potentially affecting both learning experiences and perceived realism.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Nimrod Shanit, Carina Heyer

Sources

Fink, S., Bursens, P., & Harzem, L. (2023, October 11). Let us play together! Takeaways from five collaborative online simulations. *Active Learning in Political Science*. <https://activelearningps.com/2023/10/11/lets-play-together-takeaways-from-five-collaborative-online-simulations/>

Ivens, S., & Kaiser, K. (2021). Online-Planspiele als Wegbereiter für internationale und digitale Hochschullehre. In *Geschäftsstelle beim Stifterverband* (Ed.), *Digitalisierung in Studium und Lehre gemeinsam gestalten: Innovative Formate, Strategien und Netzwerke* (pp. 533-551). Springer VS. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-32849-8_30

Raiser, S., Warkalla, B., Schneider, A., & Kaiser, K. (2018). Will it blend? Combining online and on-site elements in simulation games. In P. Bursens, V. Donche, D. Gijbels, & P. Spooren (Eds.), *Simulations of decision-making as active learning tools: Design and effects of political science simulations* (pp. 77-92). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-74147-5_7